

The network beyond the network: the potential of FabLabs as partners in participatory environmental monitoring efforts

Óscar González, Rebecca Anne Peters

*Óscar González, Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia
Barcelona, Spain*

oscar@fablabbcn.org

*Rebecca Anne Peters, Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia
Barcelona, Spain*

rebecca.peters@iaac.net

Abstract

This speculative paper analyses the theoretical potential for FabLabs to take part in participatory environmental monitoring efforts using open technologies on a large scale and contribute to reporting networks in Europe. It explores where FabLabs could fit into the European environmental monitoring ecosystem, while considering their role as often situated at the crossroads between various stakeholder groups, and presenting potential venues of collaboration between FabLabs and traditional actors within environmental monitoring. The argumentation for this paper leverages the multifaceted role of FabLabs, positing that they can provide access to infrastructure, training, skills and beyond, and therefore have the potential to play a pivotal role in participatory environmental monitoring efforts as a network, ultimately acting as an agent that enables both, long-term sustainable engagement, and large scale data collection. This potential is explored through analysis of experiential data in the provision of low-cost environmental monitoring devices and the support to beneficiaries from a Fablab perspective, which is complemented with existing data regarding FabLabs' skill sets and manufacturing capabilities; interests, motivations, and current activities; and finally, their location in relation to points of interest specific to environmental monitoring that enhance this potential. Taken together, this analysis seeks to consider the scalability of participatory environmental monitoring activities within the FabLab network itself, through multi-stakeholder collaboration between traditional actors and FabLabs, the potential impact of such partnerships, and suggestions for next steps.

Keywords

civic participation, environmental monitoring, scalability assessment, low-cost sensors, open technologies

1 Purpose

This paper analyses the potential for FabLabs to be part of participatory environmental monitoring efforts on a large scale, using low-cost, sensor-based technologies. The purpose of the analysis is to present potential opportunities for one-to-one partnerships on a local scale, as well as collective and coordinated approaches towards environmental monitoring that may involve various nodes of the FabLab Network. Given the existing and potential relationships that FabLabs have with local and broader actors in civil society, industry, academia or institutional domains, these connections and coordinated efforts may condition and enhance the outcomes in terms of the collected data quality, its completeness, and usefulness. Finally, while focusing primarily on both air quality and marine science fields, the results and conclusions are not necessarily limited to those areas. As part of this analysis, this text primarily considers the European context, but the analysis could be extrapolated to other regions of the world.

1.1 Background

Aiming to organise practices for non-conventional data collection methods, Piera (2024) presents approaches for extending environmental monitoring observational capabilities with citizen science and, in a broader sense, participatory methods. In his work, Piera uses the concepts of structured data collection (where conventional observations are complemented with data from volunteers who follow pre-established methodologies generating data as accurately as possible) or unstructured data collection (where the number of observations is maximized by expanding the number of contributions, for instance by generating more motivations to participate). Beyond both forms, conventional data collection methods aim to collect data as accurately as possible, with well-structured methods and clearly defined sampling strategies.

Typically, official monitoring schemes are based on measurements taken by Environmental Protection Agencies, at either local or national levels, which are specialised parts of the government responsible for monitoring the environment (such as, for instance, air or water quality monitoring). These agencies collaborate with research institutions and develop policies, advising governments in their programs regarding air quality. Governments have the responsibility of implementing measures for the protection of the health of humans and the environment, and they need to align their internal legislation with supranational legislation, such as the Air Quality Directive in Europe. In addition, research institutions, universities, and industry conduct studies on how to better monitor environmental parameters, develop new monitoring technologies, and provide scientific insights into the causes and impacts of pollution (CitiObs Consortium, 2025).

We argue that FabLabs can facilitate processes for both structured and unstructured environmental data collection with low-cost, open technologies, complementary to conventional data collection methods currently part of official environmental monitoring schemes. Firstly, we argue that structured data collection can be facilitated based on the concepts introduced above, focusing on the role of FabLabs as “enablers” for local processes, given the range of skills and socio-technical capabilities within FabLab nodes, promoting connections with local stakeholders and environmental monitoring initiatives (Gonzalez, 2024). Secondly, we argue for the strong potential that coordinated efforts may lead to when “orchestrating” unstructured data collection, given the large number of FabLabs in the European territory, while taking into account considerations for the collected data to be enhanced on various fronts, particularly in terms of usefulness and overall quality. When using sensors as a primary source for data collection, this data enhancement can take place when establishing relationships with expert networks or data aggregators that can strengthen the quality of collected data (Hassani et al, 2025), or by establishing comparable methods such as those already in place in the metrological field.

The environmental monitoring projects that are the focus of this analysis typically involve the use of simple hardware to collect environmental data, interfacing with low-cost sensors (in the order of 100 euros) that can send data to an online platform where it can be accessed, visualised, and stored by the owners of the hardware. Devices can be either built by participants or provided as ready-built kits, and they are deployed in various locations, generally chosen by participants, using their own resources to provide electricity or internet connectivity (Kumar et al, 2015).

Various environmental monitoring initiatives have taken root in FabLabs and likeminded spaces given the increased maturity and affordability of environmental monitoring techniques. Several factors affect this phenomena, including: (1) the broader availability of low-cost sensors for air quality monitoring that can be interfaced with Arduino-like technologies, typical to these spaces; (2) the rise in open-source data gathering infrastructures, and documentation available for the creation of these infrastructures; and (3) the increased interest by academic and government institutions in the potential use of these technologies (Kumar et al, 2015). In parallel, there is an incremental institutionalisation and perceived value of participatory processes in some areas of the world (primarily in Europe), as well as increased attention to civic monitoring schemes, and their importance for environmental conservation efforts (Suman et al, 2023).

Environmental monitoring projects have in many cases received attention from academic or institutional stakeholders. In some cases, FabLabs themselves have been the initiators of such projects, such as Smart Citizen in Fab Lab Barcelona (Camprodon et al, 2019), or sensor.community, in which many FabLabs worldwide take part (Sensor.community, n.d.). Data generated by these initiatives has been given increased attention by environmentally focused institutions and data aggregators, in particular regarding topics such as air quality monitoring, where the increased amount of data has resulted in an augmentation of the capacity by official monitoring schemes.

As part of this ecosystem, FabLabs have taken part in participatory environmental monitoring initiatives either by creating them (such as the above-mentioned Smart Citizen project by Fab Lab Barcelona) or collaborating with them (such as various FabLabs participating in sensor.community). These initiatives play a critical role in complementing, supporting, or being the primary source of information, to the environmental monitoring efforts by government agencies, in some cases regardless of their initial purpose. Increased attention and funding has been given to the role of these initiatives, and we argue that FabLabs have the potential to take part in these relationships and activities in various forms. To do so, we analyse their potential role as facilitators of local engagement processes, the potential for providing technical support, or to act as data collectors themselves. However, given that each FabLab has a unique profile, this analysis is to be considered from a general sense and not individual to each FabLab. For some, a stronger alignment may be found with one role within the ecosystem than another; for example, a FabLab within an academic research institution will likely align more closely with academia and fulfill technical needs, while one that has formed close ties with community centers or artist groups might more closely overlap with civil society and support engagement processes. That being said, in a general sense FabLabs almost always exist in the in-between spaces, less clearly demarcated than other traditional stakeholders. Finally, the ultimate purpose of this analysis is to understand what the potential next steps are to increase data usability and validity, which may enhance the uptake of the results of such monitoring efforts.

2 Methodology

The analysis draws from two sources: first, it considers results from five environmental monitoring projects, spanning three years, in which Fab Lab Barcelona has been involved, providing environmental monitoring equipment as part of two transnational Open Calls. The five environmental monitoring projects benefited from access to low-cost instrumentation as part of the MINKE Project (Grant #101008724), and were located in Italy, Ireland, and Germany and collected data with varying overall durations between three months to two years. A set of project reports, alongside experiential data on the process as technology provider, was used as the basis for this analysis. These reports were generated by the beneficiaries of those open calls; they received a varying number of low-cost sensors in order to perform their activities, at no cost, as well as support in order to deploy and use the devices. While project reports have inherent biases and a limited scope, they offer invaluable insight into these types of projects with detailed commentary on expectations and potential issues that arose throughout the project. The second area of analysis includes existing data on Fablabs such as resources and skills, motivation, location and impact by numbers. Information was collected from existing data in FabLab repositories, as well as open datasets and resources at a European level. Though part of the FabLab data is self-reported and therefore might have gaps due to lack of data or obsolete data, the information offers a broad picture of global skills and motivations that gives insight into the network as a whole.

Based on the results and analysis derived from the project reports, we identify opportunities for FabLabs to be involved in environmental monitoring, either by leveraging their technical skills (manufacturing, design, and development of technical solutions) or their community skills (such as education and community engagement), that can be implemented locally, but contribute to both structured or unstructured data collection efforts.

3 Data

The initial set of cases from which we draw the expectations for FabLabs to be involved in environmental monitoring efforts is based on the results of five activity reports, delivered after the conclusion of two transnational open calls carried out within the MINKE project, in which Fab Lab Barcelona was a provider of sensor solutions and technical support for air and water quality monitoring. These activities are described in the MINKE project reports, and provided by the beneficiaries of the sensors which, as indicated above, have limitations in terms of completeness. The summaries of these reports are available on the project's website (MINKE Consortium, D6.1, 2025) and span activities in Milano (Italy), Dublin (Ireland), Konstanz (Germany), and two in Sligo (Ireland). Based on the approach to data collection in their activities, these projects can be categorised as either: (a) citizen science projects that make use of open technologies to collect environmental data, or; (b) environmental monitoring projects that use low-cost sensors in order to collect data with higher spatial resolution at a lower cost than traditional monitoring schemes. Datasets for the data collection are available in MINKE's Zenodo community (Hollenbach et al., 2025; Gharbia et al., 2025; Saliu et al. 2025, Cocco et al. 2025) and described in the above mentioned project report.

Next, in order to understand factors that may condition the involvement of FabLabs, the following existing sources were used for this analysis:

- 1) Regarding analysis of resources and skills within FabLabs, data is extracted from existing FabLab profiles on [fablabs.io](https://api.fablabs.io), where FabLabs report both resources and specialisations. Data is extracted directly from <https://api.fablabs.io>.
- 2) Motivations for involvement are evaluated based on data collected as part of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) assessment, based on data gathered by a FabLab working group which was formed in 2017 and has been collecting FabLab SDG profiles through the present (Hijden, et al, 2024).
- 3) Geographical information used to consider proximity of FabLabs to points of interest for both air and water monitoring. In the case of air quality monitoring, proximity is evaluated in regards to air quality reference stations, extracted from the European Environment Agency (EEA) Air Quality Measurements reported within AQ e-Reporting (EEA, n.d.). In the case of water monitoring, the proximity of FabLabs will be evaluated in reference to bodies of water, by using European Coastline shapefiles, available at EUROSTAT datasets with polygon files (EuroGeographics, 2024).

4 Findings/Analysis

4.1 Expectations

Extracted from the MINKE project reports, particularly from collaborators in Dublin, Milano and Konstanz, primary expectations of the beneficiaries to low-cost sensors in citizen science projects (either community organizers or citizen scientists) seem to be the ease of use of the technologies and the facilitation of the setup and deployment of the sensors. In this regard, the ability to onboard participants to monitoring schemes, by reducing barriers such as sensor connection to Wi-Fi networks seem to be a priority for participants receiving the sensors, as well as minimal maintenance requirements for the monitoring network (handling when sensors go offline, or have a hardware problem). Additional expectations were expressed by the need to improve some aspects of the technical design (MINKE Consortium, D6.1, 2025).

Surprisingly, users did not express concerns about data quality when using the sensors in citizen science projects, or at least they are not mentioned in the reports. However, it is unclear how users processed the data, and what corrections were applied to the datasets generated by the sensors.

Finally, given the project expectations, as well as the amount of sensors requested by the majority of projects (10+ sensors), and the spatial distribution of the sensors, participants prioritise the density and availability of data, both at spatial and temporal dimensions, which indirectly implies that the technical solutions should be low-cost, simple to use and deploy, and easy to maintain. An aspect not cited in the reports but frequently

considered in internal discussions with users was the engagement of participants, as well as decaying interest in the monitoring schemes as the project unfolded.

The environmental monitoring projects involved in the open calls were primarily in Dublin, Sligo and Konstanz. In the case of Dublin and Konstanz, they had a mixed approach together with participatory methods. The primary concern by users in this aspect was regarding the maintenance of the devices, and the needs for repairs, which when deployed in remote areas, required visits by the users. The inability to check the status of the device remotely was a concern by some users, as well as difficulties devising solutions for powering the sensors, for instance, using a solar panel. In cases where repairs were needed, users were guided remotely on the diagnosis and repair process when possible, otherwise the device was recalled and fixed at Fab Lab Barcelona, which involved the shipment of the components and data loss in the collection process. It is worth noting that some of the devices received by Barcelona during that repair process had internal components that were simply disconnected after deployment, which could have been solved onsite with support from a trained technician.

Additionally, although not explicitly mentioned in the reports, users requested more complex units than the ones originally envisioned as part of the open calls offer. This required some technical adaptations of the open call offer, which also required improvements as a result of the issues encountered during sensor deployments. Finally, the users that received more technically complex sensor units had a higher interest in data quality, as the use of these units was targeted towards experts, hence not involving citizen science approaches.

4.2 Analysis of opportunities

Based on MINKE project reports, the following venues of collaboration have been identified as potentially interesting to explore. They are divided into two main categories:

1. Technical opportunities related to:
 - a. design and fabrication of custom solutions via rapid prototyping,
 - b. sensor development and integration into open data loggers,
 - c. maintenance and technical support for existing monitoring schemes.
2. Social opportunities related to:
 - a. community engagement,
 - b. support and training to non-experts.

Technical opportunities

One of the immediate venues for collaboration with FabLabs is the design, development and fabrication of custom solutions via rapid prototyping, which is a core activity in all FabLabs. This would involve skills already available to each of the FabLab Network members, and adoption barriers for this scheme would typically be non-technical, and generally related to economic agreements and the perceived benefits of the collaboration by both parties.

More involved development of, for instance, sensors and data collection systems would require additional skills that may not be readily available in all FabLabs: specific knowledge about sensors and measurement principles, or firmware development as well as data collection platforms. However, this presents opportunities for training by experts in the field. On a general note, the development of new systems may not be necessary, as existing open solutions already exist (such as Smart Citizen), but these existing solutions would certainly benefit from better synergies with experts to improve the maturity of their systems.

Finally, in the context of MINKE, a venue for collaboration that would have been most beneficial to technology users is of onsite technical support. However, the benefit to local FabLabs is rather limited, and would involve little to no benefit for them unless combined with other approaches that can help establish a long-term partnership with the collaborating institutions.

Social opportunities

Central to the FabLab Ethos is openness to the community, as they are “available as a community resource, offering open access for individuals as well as scheduled access to programs” (CBA, 2012). Beyond the openness aspect, this reflects not only the possibility of accessing FabLab resources by individuals, but the general vision of FabLabs as a space where FabLab members are accustomed to engaging with the local community, as well as providing training on the use of machines, manufacturing methods, or digital skills.

This in fact presents the strongest venue of collaboration with FabLabs as “enablers” and facilitators of community engagement processes, that can be of great use to citizen science or participatory monitoring schemes (Gonzalez, 2024). Given that they have additional skills in training individuals of all backgrounds, the adaptability of FabLabs to interdisciplinary exchanges and their capacity to offer their skills and space to provide training is an especially interesting venue for collaboration if proper acknowledgement is provided, and accompanied by fair economic support.

As a summary, Table 1 offers a rundown of these opportunities and categorises them based on their likelihood of success.

Table 1: Opportunities for FabLabs organized based on likelihood of success

Category	ID	Venue of collaboration	Potential benefit to users	Potential benefit to Fab Lab
Technical opportunities	T1	Design and fabrication of custom solutions via rapid prototyping	Medium.	Medium. More beneficial if long-term partnerships are sought.
	T2	Sensor development and integration	High.	Medium. Needs additional skills which may not be available.
	T3	Maintenance and technical support for existing monitoring schemes	High.	Low, unless coordinated with other opportunities.
Community opportunities	C1	Community engagement	High.	High. More beneficial if not on a volunteer basis.
	C2	Support and training to non-experts	Medium.	High. More beneficial if not on a volunteer basis.

4.3 Analysis of factors

At the time of writing, there are a total 2621 FabLabs worldwide, with a total of 1015 FabLabs in Europe in 31 different countries (including Norway, the United Kingdom, and Switzerland), out of which 645, according to the FabLab repository, are active. The FabLab Network repository includes additional information on each FabLab, such as node capability (according to a predefined list), and links to additional resources such a repository of FabLabs with SDG profiles. Though it would be useful to have a classification system distinguishing FabLabs linked

to industry or academia, no such classification exists. Therefore, these potential synergies are extrapolated based on node capabilities, activities, and locations.

Assessment by node capability

According to the registry in fablabs.io (Fab Lab Network, n.d.) the capabilities of FabLabs are categorized as:

- 3D printing
- CNC milling
- Circuit production (electronics)
- Laser cutting
- Precision milling
- Vinyl cutting

Figure 1 shows the aggregated capabilities in European FabLabs, the most common ones being 3D printing and laser cutting, interesting for T1, T2 and T3 from Table 1. Precision milling and circuit production are last, which would potentially be interesting for T2, while they are all cross-cutting for C1 and C2 indirectly.

Figure 1. Distribution of capabilities in FabLabs

Assessment by node activity

In recent years, the FabLab Network has gained more awareness regarding the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)¹, and has started developing a self-promoted initiative for identifying SDG profiles that each one of the FabLab Network members follow (Hijden et.al, 2024). This profile can serve as an indication of FabLab interests and core activities.

At the time of writing, a total of 666 FabLabs have completed a SDG profile, 271 of which are located in Europe. Using SDG6, SDG13, SDG14 and SDG15 (at a lower level) as indicators of activities related to environmental monitoring objectives, Table 2 shows the results extracted from the analysis:

¹ United Nation SDGs: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

Table 2. FabLabs aligned with relevant SDGs to MINKE

SDG Number	Description	Number of FabLabs aligned with the SDG	Proportion to total amount of FabLabs registered in SDGs
SDG6	Clean water and sanitation	8	3%
SDG13	Climate action	39	14%
SDG14	Life below water	9	3%
SDG15	Life on land	15	5%

In addition to the above mentioned SDGs, which have a direct relationship with environmental topics, SDG4 (Quality education - Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all) is notably the SDG with the highest amount of subscribers, with a total of 223 FabLabs out of 271 with an SDG profile in Europe.

In addition to the alignment with SDG4, an additional commitment to education is reflected in the total number of European FabLabs that have been active in the FabAcademy program over the last four years (a combined value of 44 since 2022) (Figure 2):

Figure 2. Active nodes in FabAcademy in Europe in the last four years

This reflects the interest in FabLabs to not only work on a shared educational program, but also indicates their capability to teach the variety of skills that are part of the program: 3D modeling, scanning, printing, electronics design, programming and production, integration of sensors and actuators, machining processes, as well as project management skills.

Assessment by node location

In addition to the analysis on activity and capability, node locations were also analysed.

In terms of air quality monitoring, data from the EEA's discomap service (EEA, n.d.) was used to gather information on reference stations in Europe and their proximity to FabLabs which could deploy low-cost sensors.

The retrieved data from the EEA's service used stations from 10 different countries (Belgium, Poland, Slovakia, Spain, Germany, Estonia, Sweden, France, Austria, and Romania) that had air quality monitoring stations active in 2024. Data from remaining European countries was not accessed as it was not available at the time of writing. These stations, 4559 monitoring in 2319 municipalities, monitor a wide range of pollutants. In order to perform this analysis, a selected list of pollutants was considered, including only those stations that monitor pollutants that can be captured by low-cost sensors, such as PM10, PM2.5, PM1, CO, NO2, CO2, resulting in a total of 3903 stations. An additional analysis is done considering only PM2.5, a common pollutant monitored with low-cost sensors, which is monitored in the same amount of stations.

Based on this data, and on data on the geographical location of FabLabs in Europe, official monitoring stations that monitor at least PM2.5 are categorized based on their proximity to a FabLab in the following intervals:

- Less than 5 km
- Between 5 km and 25 km
- Between 25 km and 50 km
- Farther than 50 km

Table 3 shows the value count for each category:

Table 3. Number of stations categorised based on their proximity to a FabLab

Category	Number of Stations
Less than 5 km	355
Between 5 to 25 km	388
Between 20 to 50 km	351
Farther than 50 km	715

This shows that more than 350 air quality monitoring stations are situated less than 5km from FabLabs in Europe. In other words, based on this number, considering that each FabLab could have the capacity to deploy several low-cost air quality monitors in their local context, the potential for the collected data to be referenced and compared to the official monitoring stations, augmenting the capacity of the local monitoring network, is not negligible. As an example, aiming to visually showcase the geographic potential, various locations are shown in Figure 3, depicting the location of air quality monitoring stations (in blue dots), and FabLabs (in dark red dots) in different European cities.

Figure 3: Locations of air quality monitoring stations (blue) and FabLabs (red)

In terms of water monitoring, we focus on the potential monitoring of Europe’s coastline. For this analysis, EUROSTAT datasets with polygon files (EuroGeographics, 2024) in addition to the EEA’s European coastline shapefile (EEA, 2018) were used to perform a rolling merge on the FabLab’s location to determine their distance from Europe’s coastline. This analysis categorised FabLabs with respect to their distance from the coast in the following intervals:

- Less than 5 km
- Between 5 km and 25 km
- Between 25 km and 50 km
- Farther than 50 km

Table 4 shows the value count for each category:

Table 4. FabLab node location and capability assessment

Category	Number of FabLabs	Number of FabLabs with all capabilities
Less than 5 km	123	23
Between 5 to 25 km	76	17
Between 20 to 50 km	51	8
Farther than 50 km	367	84

Figure 4. FabLabs distribution in Europe and Northern African countries.
 Copyright on the use of Geospatial information by © EuroGeographics.
 FabLab data available at fablabs.io (FabLabs Online Resources | FabLabs, n.d.)

This shows that 250 FabLabs in Europe are situated in an area less than 50 km away from the coastline, and that 199 could be considered coastal, as they are 25 km or less. Figure 4 shows a map of these FabLabs, with those in red, orange and yellow as those with closer distance to the coastline, as per the categories indicated above. If expanded to FabLabs also in Northern African countries as well as Turkey and other nearby countries, the total number of FabLabs within 25 km of the coast increases to 311. Considering that each FabLab can manufacture their own equipment at a reduced cost, campaigns involving monitoring of coastal regions such as the Mediterranean sea, have great potential if done together with FabLabs in coastal regions.

Finally, when filtering those FabLabs with all the capabilities listed above in section 4.3.1 (a total of 132 FabLabs), the number of nodes with a distance lower than 50 km is reduced to 48. However, this should not be taken as a direct measure of the capacity of the FabLab, but rather an indication of the equipment available in their facilities.

5 Research limitations and implications

There are a number of limitations to this research which relate to both scope and available information which will be considered in this section. Broadly speaking, however, while the research is limited by the factors considered below, this does not invalidate its analysis, and its conclusions can be useful to guide future coordinated environmental data collection efforts. First, the use of project reports from the MINKE Project (Grant #101008724), while having a limited scope, provides invaluable insight into the expectations of potential partners, thus the reports were cited to exemplify first-hand experiences to support the overall hypothetical potential of the FabLab network as a potential enabler of (large-scale) environmental monitoring efforts. However, their limited scope means that, while the themes seen in expectations could extrapolate to offer broader insight, they might not hold true in all situations. Second, by definition, not all makerspaces or hackerspaces are FabLabs; while this research is limited to FabLabs, it could be made broader to include other spaces of a similar type. However, information on such spaces, due to their independent nature leaves a great deal of incomplete information. Third, as mentioned briefly in the methodology section of this paper, FabLabs themselves are not fully defined by what is online (on fablabs.io, within other studies, and as reflected in completed SDG profiles). As detailed in the analysis section, it would be useful to have other classification systems available based on existing links to industry and academia, as well as more detailed technical expertise within repository profiles, which is something that could be suggested to strengthen the existing database in its potential for this kind of research. Specifically in the case of SDG profiles, a lack of data on many FabLabs as well as limitations in visibility beyond four SDGs per profile mean that interest or willingness to engage in these topics is not fully known. Furthermore, technical expertise gaps mean that while the network as a whole offers great potential, not all individual FabLabs would be suitable partners for large-scale environmental monitoring. Likewise, while the distributed network has proven successful in educational efforts, the difficulties inherent to a distributed network would likely need to be overcome in this new context for the FabLab network as a whole. Third, this research has limited its focus to Europe, particularly because funding opportunities from the European Commission are often restricted to this area, making a broader scope more difficult to achieve. Finally, there is always the possibility that there are unknown existing or potential initiatives and partnerships with FabLabs that are not recorded on the existing research, this was seen in González, et al. (2024) during interviews with FabLabs.

6 Practical implications

This research has a number of practical implications, both short and long term. The first and most clear implication in our view is the need to further assess the interest to form a working group within the network regarding FabLabs as nodes, or enablers, of large-scale environmental monitoring efforts. FabLabs have the technical expertise and the manufacturing capabilities in many cases to support these efforts, and their interests often align with the SDGs that encompass issues of environmental conservation and education. Finally, their locations can offer key points of overlap with locations of interest (both in proximity to reference units, and proximity to bodies of water in the case of water monitoring efforts). A working group could act as a common

space for sharing knowledge, experiences, methods and instruments, and, in the future, coordinate environmental monitoring efforts, while helping FabLabs to find ways to collaborate or fill in the gaps of knowledge necessary to do so (for instance expertise in sensors or in environmental monitoring). Likewise, with the inertia that comes with such a great number of FabLabs these efforts could bring low-cost sensor data collection efforts beyond unstructured data collection, towards data coverage that offers reliability and long-term, widespread monitoring.

Finally, the future working group may benefit from current practices in other activities of the FabLab Network such as standardisation of their processes, which can enhance the intended outcomes. This is currently seen in well-known programmes such as FabAcademy, where the coordination's effort into sharing a syllabus, inventory, and teaching materials (the practices) facilitates mobility among the alumni (the intended outcome). A similar approach could be extrapolated to monitoring efforts, and understood as a way to increase data usability and impact (the intended outcome) by enhancing its comparability and interoperability by offering agreed upon options for *fabbable* low-cost sensors, or reporting platforms that support standard data formats that can later be accessed by data aggregators (the practices).

7 Original value of paper

This paper offers innovative analysis of FabLabs in Europe and their potential role within environmental monitoring. To the best of the knowledge of the authors, no other analysis of this type has been performed looking at this specific combination of actors, skill assessment, and location analysis of a network as widespread as the FabLab community. While theoretical, the need for this analysis is twofold, first, it is clear that there is untapped potential within the FabLab network to engage with and support monitoring efforts, and second because a network of this size could provide a way to scale monitoring efforts with widespread impact, especially when carried out in coordinated manners, sharing both resources, knowledge and methods among participating nodes.

8 Conclusion

Based on previous sections, we conclude that there is a high potential for involving FabLabs in environmental observing projects and initiatives for various reasons. Firstly, FabLabs have a variety of capacities, both from a technical and community engagement perspective, that justifies their involvement as “enablers” in environmental monitoring projects. Based on the cumulative experience of Fab Lab Barcelona with the coordination of the Smart Citizen project, two approaches to environmental data collection with open technologies and low-cost sensors have been identified: a participatory approach, and a “conventional” one. Both approaches could benefit in various degrees from the involvement of FabLabs, although the most promising benefit comes down to their role as “enablers” in the multi-stakeholder processes that take place in participatory schemes. The ability of FabLabs to act as multifaceted actors that support both technical and social aspects is well described and justified in previous sections. Secondly, their core activities are well aligned with the potential needs that these projects would require, such as manufacturing services, education, prototyping, and community engagement. It is worth noting however that the alignment of FabLabs with SDG profiles that align with environmental protection efforts is noticeably not as strong, thus, exploring connections via training and education would have a stronger possibility for alignment, although these relationships are worth exploring in any case based on core FabLab drivers and motivations analysed in previous sections. The case is stronger if proposed collaborations are devised with opportunities for the FabLab to grow and be involved in local activities that have an impact in their surroundings as well as those which enhance the FabLab's future activity and capacity.

Other venues of collaboration could be beneficial to “conventional” academic monitoring schemes in a technical support sense, and in some cases of prototyping and development, although specific skills are required (sensor development for instance), and the involvement of FabLabs in such processes should be clearly defined and

compensated fairly in economic terms, while being targeted to generate a long-term relationship that is beneficial to both groups.

In terms of numbers, the large number of FabLabs in Europe may justify by itself a coordinated effort for environmental data collection. In the air quality field, the number of FabLabs less than 5 km away from official environmental monitoring stations amounts to more than 350 in Europe, while it rises to more than 700 when considering 20 km or less. In the case of marine observation, as seen in previous sections, approximately 200 are located in coastal environments in Europe, and more than 300 if including nearby regions, numbers substantial enough to justify explorations on how they could potentially support marine observation efforts. This approach clearly aligns with innovative approaches to data collection that can improve quality and usefulness of the data by increased completeness and accuracy. Beyond the most obvious number of FabLabs, the fact that all FabLabs share equipment that could replicate instruments, not only reduces cost, but also increases potential replicability and comparability of data, supporting the implementation of large-scale participatory monitoring schemes.

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No AI has been used in the production of the content of this paper, in either text generation or correction.

References

- Berti Suman, A., Balestrini, M., Haklay, M., & Schade, S. (2023). When concerned people produce environmental information: A need to re-think existing legal frameworks and governance models? *Citizen Science Theory and Practice*, 8(1), 10. doi:10.5334/cstp.496
- Camprodon, G., González, Ó., Barberán, V., Pérez, M., Smári, V., de Heras, M. Á., & Bizzotto, A. (2019). Smart Citizen Kit and Station: An open environmental monitoring system for citizen participation and scientific experimentation. *HardwareX*, 6(e00070), e00070. doi:10.1016/j.ohx.2019.e00070
- CBA (2012). The Fab Charter. Retrieved 10 December 2012, from <https://fab.cba.mit.edu/about/charter/>
- CitiObs Consortium, CitiObs Environmental Monitoring Toolkit, n.d. 2025, <https://toolkits.citiobs.eu/citiobs-environmental-monitoring-toolkit/>
- Cocco, C., & Crowley, S. (2025). MINKE TNA Open Call - ACTIVATE [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15019991>
- EuroGeographics Countries boundaries data, 2024, © EuroGeographics, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/administrative-units/countries>
- European Environment Agency, Discomap Service, n.d. <https://discomap.eea.europa.eu/index/>
- European Environment Agency, European Coastline Shapefile, 2018, <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/eea-coastline-for-analysis-2/gis-data/eea-coastline-polygon>
- Fab Labs online Resources | FabLabs. (n.d.). FabLabs.io - the Fab Lab Network. <https://www.fablabs.io/>
- Ferdinand, J., Petschow, U., & Dickel, S. (2016). The decentralized and networked future of value creation: 3D Printing and its Implications for Society, Industry, and Sustainable Development. Springer.
- Gershenfeld, Neil. *Fab: The Coming Revolution on Your Desktop--from Personal Computers to Personal Fabrication*. Basic Books, 2008.
- González, Ó., Calvo Juárez, M., & Guy, J. (2024, August 5). An inquiry into Fab Labs as enablers for environmental protection initiatives. Fab 24 "Fabricating Equity" Research Papers (Fab24), Puebla, Mexico. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13221337>
- Hassani, A., Salamalikis, V., Schneider, P., Stebel, K., & Castell, N. (2025). A scalable framework for harmonizing, standardization, and correcting crowd-sourced low-cost sensor PM2.5 data across Europe. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 380(125100), 125100. doi:10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.125100

Óscar González, Rebecca Anne Peters: The network beyond the network: The potential of FabLabs as partners in participatory environmental monitoring efforts

- Hijden, P. van . der ., Elnwisy, N., & Caycho, V. (2024, August 5). Fablabs and SDGs: from Awareness via Alignment to Accountability and Impact-by-Design. Fab 24 "Fabricating Equity" Research Papers (Fab24), Puebla, Mexico. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13221331>
- Hollenbach, P. (2025). MINKE TNA Open Call - SmartCoKliMINKE [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15019202>
- How MIT's fab labs scaled around the world. (2023, June 5). MIT News | Massachusetts Institute of Technology. <https://news.mit.edu/2023/how-mits-fab-labs-scaled-around-world-0605>
- Liñán, S., Salvador, X., Álvarez, A., Comaposada, A., Sanchez, L., Aparicio, N., Rodero, I., & Piera, J. (2022). A new theoretical engagement framework for citizen science projects: using a multi-temporal approach to address long-term public engagement challenges. *Environmental Research Letters*, 17(10), 105006. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac939d>
- Kumar, P., Morawska, L., Martani, C., Biskos, G., Neophytou, M., Di Sabatino, S., ... Britter, R. (2015). The rise of low-cost sensing for managing air pollution in cities. *Environment International*, 75, 199–205. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2014.11.019
- MINKE consortium D1.2 (2024), Analysis of metrological requirements of stakeholders and users, Jukka Seppälä, Rajesh Nair, George Petihakis, Florence Salvetat, Andrew King, Paola Fisicaro, and Susan Hartman
- MINKE consortium D1.1 (2022), Report on existing metrology infrastructures in Europe in terms of equipment used, methods employed and metrology variables, Paola Fisicaro, George Petihakis, Sylvia Christodoulaki.
- MINKE consortium D4.10 (2025), Strategic analysis of the integration with knowledge-based citizen communities. Piera, J., Honorato, D., Colom, L., González, Ó. Metrology for Integrated Marine Management and Knowledge-Transfer Network, MINKE.
- MINKE consortium D6.1 (2025), VA to low cost instrumentation for environmental monitoring, calls and activity report, Óscar González, Rebecca Anne Peters. Metrology for Integrated Marine Management and Knowledge-Transfer Network, MINKE.
- Peris-Ortiz, M., Ferreira, J. J., Farinha, L., & Fernandes, N. O. (2016). Multiple Helix ecosystems for sustainable competitiveness. In *Innovation, technology and knowledge management*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-29677-7>
- Piera, J. (2024, December 24). Better Data Quality in Citizen Science (I): Structured vs Unstructured data collection and potential biases. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14552911>
- Salem Gharbia, AHMED, T., & Banerjee, A. (2025). MINKE TNA Open Call - LOWESS [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15017901>
- Saliu, F. (2025). MINKE TNA Open Call - Sail2Science [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15021707>
- Sensor.community, n.d. <https://sensor.community/>
- The Fab foundation. (n.d.). <https://fabfoundation.org/>